

WP2 Facilitate SNOMED CT use and raising awareness, sharing knowledge and training initiatives

D2.2 Project Website

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Executive Summary

The *Portugal SNOMED International membership 2* (SNO-PT 2) action will enable the expansion of the Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine Clinical Terms (SNOMED CT) coverage in Portugal, by renewing the status of SNOMED International membership – for the years 2025, 2026 and 2027 – which allows free distribution and use of that terminology within the Health System (public and private organisations) and other health-related entities.

This document is the Deliverable (D)2.2 *Project Website* of SNO-PT 2 action that provides an overview of the structure and content of the SNO-PT 2 webpage, detailing its different sections. It also outlines the strategy used to ensure harmonisation and a line of continuity, linking SNO-PT 2 with the preceding action *Portugal SNOMED International membership* (SNO-PT).

The webpage of SNO-PT 2 is hosted at the official Clinical Terminologies Centre (CTC) website, a Centre managed by SPMS, which is responsible for the maintenance and management of SNOMED CT in Portugal. This approach allows to simplify access to SNOMED-related information in one webpage, streamlining access to training materials and resources, as well as promoting continuous learning and capacity building among the webpage visitors, such as public in general, health professionals and stakeholders. It also facilitates the dissemination of information about the action and its main achievements.

The webpage was also designed to comply with the EU funding visibility requirements, ensuring compliance across both SNO-PT and SNO-PT 2 webpages.

The website will be the main digital communication channel to provide information about the action and its main objectives on dissemination, communication and training initiatives, to raise awareness on the use of SNOMED CT International terminology for primary and secondary use of health data.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

CTC	Centro de Terminologias Clínicas (Clinical Terminologies Centre)
D	Deliverable(s)
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
SNOMED-CT	Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine – Clinical Terms
SNO-PT	Portugal SNOMED International membership
SNO-PT 2	Portugal SNOMED International membership 2
SPMS	SPMS – Serviços Partilhados do Ministério da Saúde, E.P.E. (SPMS, Shared Services of Ministry of Health)
WCAG	Web Content Accessibility Guidelines
WP	Work Package(s)

1. Introduction

The *Portugal SNOMED International membership 2* (SNO-PT 2) action will enable the expansion of the Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine Clinical Terms (SNOMED CT) coverage in Portugal, by renewing the status of SNOMED International membership – for the years 2025, 2026 and 2027 – which allows free distribution and use of that terminology within the Health System (public and private organisations) and other health-related entities.

Building on the structure established by the *Portugal SNOMED International membership* (SNO-PT) action, which took place from January 2023 to December 2024, SNO-PT 2 continues the objective of maintaining and expanding the use of SNOMED CT in Portugal.

As part of its awareness, knowledge sharing, dissemination, communication and training strategy, the first action developed a dedicated SNO-PT webpage within the Clinical Terminologies Centre (CTC) official website, under the SNOMED CT tab, ensuring a clear and consistent connection to the terminology. The CTC is a centre managed by SPMS, which is the national entity responsible for the maintenance and management of SNOMED CT in Portugal.

To build upon the initial efforts and consolidate the information on SNOMED CT, SNO-PT 2 has its own page hosted under the SNOMED CT tab, following a similar approach as SNO-PT and keeping the link between these two EU co-funded actions. This approach allows to simplify access to SNOMED-related information in one webpage, streamlining access to training materials and resources, as well as promoting continuous learning and capacity building among the webpage visitors, such as public in general, health professionals and stakeholders. It also facilitates the dissemination of information about the action and its main achievements.

As stated in the Grant Agreement (GA), Work Package (WP) 2 *Facilitate SNOMED CT use and raising awareness, sharing knowledge and training initiatives* is responsible for all communication and dissemination activities of this action with the aim of raising awareness regarding its objectives, results and the ongoing national efforts to foster SNOMED CT use and expansion through SNO-PT 2. For this purpose, WP2 is responsible for the development of the SNO-PT 2 webpage that will serve as the main digital communication channel to provide information about the action.

1.1. Objective

The objective of this document is to present the SNO-PT 2 webpage structure, explaining and describing the different sections and detailing how it is harmonised with SNO-PT action, all within the CTC website. Additionally, it also shows how the SNO-PT 2 webpage complies with the required EU Co-funded rules, including the disclaimer and the EU flag.

2. Webpage structure

2.1. SNO-PT 2 webpage

The SNO-PT 2 webpage was built following the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) 2.1 to make it accessible to a wider audience, including people with visual, hearing and cognitive disabilities.

It can be accessed [here](#), and is available in both English (EN or .en) and Portuguese (PT or .pt), just alternating between “EN” and “PT” (upright corner, Figure 1).

At the CTC [website](#), users can access the SNO-PT 2 webpage by clicking on the ‘SNOMED CT’ menu. In this menu, users can find the ‘Co-financed Projects’ option, where information on both SNO-PT and SNO-PT 2 can be accessed (Figure 1).

Figure 1. CTC – Co-financed Projects

2.1.1. Co-financed Projects webpage: SNO-PT and SNO-PT 2

To maintain the connection with SNO-PT, the ‘Co-financed Projects’ webpage was updated to combine both actions – SNO-PT and SNO-PT 2 – in a seamless way. To support this connection, the webpage starts by displaying a timeline of SNO-PT and SNO-PT 2 that was created to illustrate the continuity of the activities without interruptions, from January 2023 till December 2027, as illustrated at Figure 2.

Figure 2. SNO-PT & SNO-PT 2 Timeline

Below this figure, two interactive boxes are shown, which allow users to access the two actions. These boxes clearly identify the SNO-PT 2 and SNO-PT actions with a “Learn more” button, located beneath the respective logo from which is possible to access the main information of each action, as illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. SNO-PT 2 & SNO-PT access proposal

The footer of the webpage ‘Co-financed Projects’ displays the EU co-funded flag, with text in both English and Portuguese, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. EU flags

Figure 5 illustrates the full image of ‘Co-financed Projects’ webpage.

[Home](#) | [SNOMED CT](#) | [Co-financed Projects](#)

Co-financed Projects

Co-financed projects are a key instrument for capturing European funds with the aim of promoting the sustainability of digital innovation in national healthcare systems.

To maintain the connection to SNO-PT, the "Co-financed Projects" page has been updated to integrate both actions - SNO-PT and SNO-PT 2 - in an integrated manner. To support this connection, this image presents a timeline of SNO-PT and SNO-PT 2, created to illustrate the continuity of activities without interruptions, from January 2023 to December 2027.

[← To go back](#)

Figure 5. CTC website – Co-financed Projects page

The official Logo of the SNO-PT 2 is described in D2.1 *SNOMED CT awareness raising, education and training plan* and shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. SNO-PT 2 Logo

2.1.2. SNO-PT 2-specific webpage

The SNO-PT 2-specific webpage is structured into six main sections, as detailed in the next subchapters. Each subchapter corresponds to one section of the webpage and is organised using the following strategy:

- Subchapter **Header** shows the title of the section
- **Aim** explains the goal of the section
- **Displayed text** shows the text and/or image added at the webpage

2.1.2.1. Title and Logo

Aim:

It shows the title of the action, allowing the reader to clearly identify the purpose of the webpage.

Displayed text and Logo:

Portugal SNOMED International Membership 2

2.1.2.2. Scope

Aim:

To introduce the SNO-PT 2 action, highlighting its main scope and importance, using accessible language for a wider audience.

Displayed text:

The SNO-PT 2 action, coordinated by SPMS, aims to ensure the continued and expanded use of the international standardised terminology for coding health data, SNOMED CT, in national health information systems. The use of this terminology is essential to increase semantic interoperability, supporting the development of the European Health Data Space for the provision of better healthcare at national and cross-border levels (primary use) and also for research, medical innovation, health policy-making and regulatory activities

(secondary use), thus contributing to improving the quality of health data available for these purposes.

2.1.2.3. Impact on the National Health Service (NHS)

Aim:

To describe the importance of SNO-PT 2 for enabling the free distribution and use of SNOMED CT at the Portuguese National Health Service (NHS).

In comparison to SNO-PT, the SNO-PT 2 webpage was improved with a scheme to reinforce the importance of SNOMED CT for the Health System and Health-related entities, illustrating its benefits, in the following main areas:

- Improving interoperability and communication between systems.
- Support for digital health and Electronic Health Records.
- Improving healthcare delivery.
- Support for medical research and innovation.
- Sustainability and efficiency in NHS management.

The scheme is available in English (Figure 7) and in Portuguese (Figure 8), according to what suits the reader.

Displayed text:

The use of a set of internationally standardized terminologies in healthcare, such as SNOMED CT, promotes interoperability, quality of healthcare and efficiency in the management of clinical information. It is an essential tool for the modernization and digitalization of the NHS, allowing safer, more efficient and structured access to clinical information. Its impact goes beyond interoperability, contributing to a more interconnected, innovative and citizen-centred healthcare system.

Image:

Figure 7. SNOMED CT benefits (.en)

Figure 8. SNOMED CT benefits (.pt)

2.1.2.4. Objectives of the SNO-PT 2 action

Aim:

To describe the objectives foreseen to achieve during the period of the action, as stated on the GA.

Displayed text and image:

From January 1, 2025 to December 2027:

Annual Fee

Guarantee 3 annual fees as a member of SNOMED *International* for 2025, 2026 and 2027.

Licenses

Distribute 3 new licenses of SNOMED CT clinical terminology to national partners.

Use Cases

Implement 2 new use cases.

Translated terms

Increase to 8562 the number of translated SNOMED CT terms.

Dissemination and Representation

Participate in official SNOMED *International* meetings and promote dissemination and communication activities.

Training

Organize 1 training action to support partners in using a new use case.

Figure 9. Objectives of SNO-PT 2

2.1.2.5. News

Aim:

To present links that redirect the reader to the news published with updates and information about the action, produced during its timeframe.

As of the writing this deliverable, readers can access the published news article that summarises the main results of SNO-PT and introduces the launch of SNO-PT 2.

Displayed text and image:

News

SPMS strengthens interoperability with SNOMED CT

SPMS continues to invest in improving communication between information and communication technology (ICT) systems in the health sector, encouraging the use of SNOMED CT clinical terminology in Portugal.

[Read more – SPMS](#)

Figure 10. News – Main results of SNO-PT and launch of SNO-PT 2

One can access the full notice clicking on Read more.

2.1.2.6. Results achieved

Aim:

Showcase materials related to the main outcomes of the SNO-PT 2 action, such as the benefits of SNOMED CT, dissemination and training activities, new use case developed, number of terms translated or public deliverables.

At the time of writing this document, there was not yet published information.

Displayed text:

To be published in January 2026.

2.1.2.7. EU Co-funded visibility

Aim:

To comply with the EU co-funding rules, the footer contains the disclaimer and the official EU Co-funding flag, representing the support received from the EU4Health programme, in English (EN) or Portuguese (PT) – according to the language selected – as shown in Table 1, Figure 11 and Figure 12, respectively in EN and PT. As images, both flags in EN and PT are always shown.

Displayed text:

Table 1. Disclaimer of SNO-PT 2 in English and Portuguese

EU Flag	Disclaimer
	<p><i>The SNO-PT 2 action is co-funded by the European Union, EU4Health Programme 2021-2027 under the Grant Agreement Nr 101181370. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.</i></p>
	<p><i>A ação SNO-PT 2 é cofinanciado pela União Europeia, Programa EU4Health 2021-2027 ao abrigo do Grant Agreement (Acordo de Subvenção) Nº 101181370. No entanto, os pontos de vista e opiniões expressos são exclusivamente da responsabilidade do(s) autor(es) e não refletem necessariamente os da União Europeia ou da Agência Europeia de Execução para a Saúde e o Digital (European Health and Digital Executive Agency, HaDEA). Nem a União Europeia nem a entidade concedente podem ser responsabilizados por eles.</i></p>

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Figure 11. EU Co-funding statement and flags (.en)

A ação SNO-PT 2 é cofinanciada pela União Europeia, Programa EU4Health 2021-2027 ao abrigo do Grant Agreement (Acordo de Subvenção) Nº 101181370. No entanto, os pontos de vista e opiniões expressos são exclusivamente da responsabilidade do(s) autor(es) e não refletem necessariamente os da União Europeia ou da Agência Europeia de Execução para a Saúde e o Digital (European Health and Digital Executive Agency, HaDEA). Nem a União Europeia nem a autoridade concedente podem ser responsabilizados por eles.

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Figure 12. EU Co-funding statement and flags (.pt)

Figure 13. SNO-PT 2 webpage

illustrates the full image of SNO-PT 2 webpage.

[Home](#) | [SNOMED CT](#) | [Co-financed Projects](#) | [Portugal SNOMED International Membership 2](#)

Portugal SNOMED International Membership 2

Scope

The SNO-PT 2 action, coordinated by SPMS, aims to ensure the continued and expanded use of the international standardised terminology for coding health data, SNOMED CT, in national health information systems. The use of this terminology is essential to increase semantic interoperability, supporting the development of the European Health Data Space for the provision of better healthcare at national and cross-border levels (primary use) and also for research, medical innovation, health policy-making and regulatory activities (secondary use), thus contributing to improving the quality of health data available for these purposes.

Impact on the National Health Service (NHS)

The use of a set of internationally standardised terminologies in healthcare, such as SNOMED CT, promotes interoperability, quality of healthcare and efficiency in the management of clinical information. It is an essential tool for the modernisation and digitalisation of the NHS, enabling safer, more efficient and structured access to clinical information. Its impact goes beyond interoperability, contributing to a more interconnected, innovative and citizen-centred healthcare system.

Improving Interoperability and Communication between Systems

Facilitating the exchange of information between different health systems, hospitals, clinics and professionals.

Support for Digital Health and Electronic Health Records

The integration of SNOMED CT into the NHS EHR systems improves the coding and retrieval of clinical data.

Improved Healthcare Delivery

With a standardized vocabulary, healthcare professionals have access to more accurate information about patients.

Support for Medical Research and Innovation

Structured and standardized data enable epidemiological analyses, clinical studies and the development of new medical approaches.

Sustainability and Efficiency in the Management of the NHS

The adoption of SNOMED CT contributes to a more efficient management of health resources.

Objectives of the SNO-PT 2 action

From January 1, 2025 to December 2027:

Annual Fee

Guarantee 3 annual fees as a member of SNOMED *International* for 2025, 2026 and 2027.

Licenses

Distribute 3 new licenses of SNOMED CT clinical terminology to national partners.

Use Cases

Implement 2 new use cases.

Translated terms

Increase to 8562 the number of translated SNOMED CT terms.

Dissemination and Representation

Participate in official SNOMED *International* meetings and promote dissemination and communication activities.

Training

Organize 1 training action to support partners in using a new use case.

News

SPMS strengthens interoperability with SNOMED CT

SPMS continues to invest in improving communication between information and communication technology (ICT) systems in the health sector, encouraging the use of SNOMED CT clinical terminology in Portugal.

[Read more – SPMS](#)

Results achieved

To be published in January 2026.

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Figure 13. SNO-PT 2 webpage

Annex I and Annex II present the detailed information of SNO-PT 2 webpage, respectively in English and Portuguese versions.

. Each subchapter corresponds to one section of the webpage and is organised using the following strategy:

- Subchapter **Header** shows the title of the section
- **Aim** explains the goal of the section
- **Displayed text** shows the text and/or image added at the webpage

2.1.2.8. Title and Logo

Aim:

It shows the title of the action, allowing the reader to clearly identify the purpose of the webpage.

Displayed text and Logo:

Portugal SNOMED International Membership 2

2.1.2.9. Scope

Aim:

To introduce the SNO-PT 2 action, highlighting its main scope and importance, using accessible language for a wider audience.

Displayed text:

The SNO-PT 2 action, coordinated by SPMS, aims to ensure the continued and expanded use of the international standardised terminology for coding health data, SNOMED CT, in

national health information systems. The use of this terminology is essential to increase semantic interoperability, supporting the development of the European Health Data Space for the provision of better healthcare at national and cross-border levels (primary use) and also for research, medical innovation, health policy-making and regulatory activities (secondary use), thus contributing to improving the quality of health data available for these purposes.

2.1.2.10. Impact on the National Health Service (NHS)

Aim:

To describe the importance of SNO-PT 2 for enabling the free distribution and use of SNOMED CT at the Portuguese National Health Service (NHS).

In comparison to SNO-PT, the SNO-PT 2 webpage was improved with a scheme to reinforce the importance of SNOMED CT for the Health System and Health-related entities, illustrating its benefits, in the following main areas:

- Improving interoperability and communication between systems.
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- Improving healthcare delivery.
- Support for medical research and innovation.
- Sustainability and efficiency in NHS management.

The scheme is available in English (Figure 7) and in Portuguese (Figure 8), according to what suits the reader.

Displayed text:

The use of a set of internationally standardized terminologies in healthcare, such as SNOMED CT, promotes interoperability, quality of healthcare and efficiency in the management of clinical information. It is an essential tool for the modernization and digitalization of the NHS, allowing safer, more efficient and structured access to clinical information. Its impact goes beyond interoperability, contributing to a more interconnected, innovative and citizen-centred healthcare system.

Image:

Figure 7. SNOMED CT benefits (.en)

Figure 8. SNOMED CT benefits (.pt)

2.1.2.11. Objectives of the SNO-PT 2 action

Aim:

To describe the objectives foreseen to achieve during the period of the action, as stated on the GA.

Displayed text and image:

From January 1, 2025 to December 2027:

Annual Fee

Guarantee 3 annual fees as a member of SNOMED *International* for 2025, 2026 and 2027.

Licenses

Distribute 3 new licenses of SNOMED CT clinical terminology to national partners.

Use Cases

Implement 2 new use cases.

Translated terms

Increase to 8562 the number of translated SNOMED CT terms.

Dissemination and Representation

Participate in official SNOMED *International* meetings and promote dissemination and communication activities.

Training

Organize 1 training action to support partners in using a new use case.

Figure 9. Objectives of SNO-PT 2

2.1.2.12. News

Aim:

To present links that redirect the reader to the news published with updates and information about the action, produced during its timeframe.

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SPMS continues to invest in improving communication between information and communication technology (ICT) systems in the health sector, encouraging the use of SNOMED CT clinical terminology in Portugal.

Read more – SPMS

Figure 10. News – Main results of SNO-PT and launch of SNO-PT 2

One can access the full notice clicking on [Read more](#).

2.1.2.13. Results achieved

Aim:

Showcase materials related to the main outcomes of the SNO-PT 2 action, such as the benefits of SNOMED CT, dissemination and training activities, new use case developed, number of terms translated or public deliverables.

At the time of writing this document, there was not yet published information.

Displayed text:

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2.1.2.14. EU Co-funded visibility

Aim:

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Figure 11. EU Co-funding statement and flags (.en)

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Figure 12. EU Co-funding statement and flags (.pt)

Figure 13. SNO-PT 2 webpage

illustrates the full image of SNO-PT 2 webpage.

[Home](#) | [SNOMED CT](#) | [Co-financed Projects](#) | [Portugal SNOMED International Membership 2](#)

Portugal SNOMED International Membership 2

Scope

The SNO-PT 2 action, coordinated by SPMS, aims to ensure the continued and expanded use of the international standardised terminology for coding health data, SNOMED CT, in national health information systems. The use of this terminology is essential to increase semantic interoperability, supporting the development of the European Health Data Space for the provision of better healthcare at national and cross-border levels (primary use) and also for research, medical innovation, health policy-making and regulatory activities (secondary use), thus contributing to improving the quality of health data available for these purposes.

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With a standardized vocabulary, healthcare professionals have access to more accurate information about patients.

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The adoption of SNOMED CT contributes to a more efficient management of health resources.

Objectives of the SNO-PT 2 action

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Implement 2 new use cases.

Translated terms

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Training

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News

SPMS strengthens interoperability with SNOMED CT

SPMS continues to invest in improving communication between information and communication technology (ICT) systems in the health sector, encouraging the use of SNOMED CT clinical terminology in Portugal.

[Read more – SPMS](#)

Results achieved

To be published in January 2026.

The SNO-PT 2 action is co-funded by the European Union, EU4Health Programme 2021-2027 under Grant Agreement No 101181370. However, the views and opinions expressed are solely those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority may be held responsible for them.

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Figure 13. SNO-PT 2 webpage

Annex I and Annex II present the detailed information of SNO-PT 2 webpage, respectively in English and Portuguese versions.

3. Conclusion

The strategy for the SNO-PT 2 webpage leveraged the existing efforts and building blocks of the predecessor action, SNO-PT, enabling a smoother navigation within the CTC website while maintaining key information associated with SNOMED CT, which constitutes the core centre of the action. The primary goal of this approach was to streamline access to training materials and resources, promoting continuous learning and capacity building among stakeholders, while also disseminating information about the action and its main achievements. The current layout was designed to enable its evolution, with potential to enhance as new features could be identified to improve usability over time.

Annexes

Annex I. SNO-PT 2 webpage text in English

Portugal SNOMED International Membership 2

Scope

The SNO-PT 2 action, coordinated by SPMS, aims to ensure the continued and expanded use of the international standardised terminology for coding health data, SNOMED CT, in national health information systems. The use of this terminology is essential to increase semantic interoperability, supporting the development of the European Health Data Space with a view to providing better healthcare at national and cross-border level (primary use) and also for research, medical innovation, health policy-making and regulatory activities (secondary use), thus contributing to improving the quality of health data available for these purposes.

Impact on the National Health Service (NHS)

The use of a set of internationally standardized terminologies in healthcare, such as SNOMED CT, promotes interoperability, quality of healthcare and efficiency in the management of clinical information. It is an essential tool for the modernization and digitalization of the NHS, allowing safer, more efficient and structured access to clinical information. Its impact goes beyond interoperability, contributing to a more interconnected, innovative and citizen-centred healthcare system.

Improving Interoperability and Communication between Systems

Facilitating the exchange of information between different health systems, hospitals, clinics and professionals.

Support for Digital Health and Electronic Health Records

The integration of SNOMED CT into the NHS EHR systems improves the coding and retrieval of clinical data.

Improved Healthcare Delivery

With a standardized vocabulary, healthcare professionals have access to more accurate information about patients.

Support for Medical Research and Innovation

Structured and standardized data enable epidemiological analyses, clinical studies and the development of new medical approaches.

Sustainability and Efficiency in the Management of the NHS

The adoption of SNOMED CT contributes to a more efficient management of health resources.

Objectives of the SNO-PT 2 action

From January 1, 2025 to December 2027:

Annual Fee

Guarantee 3 annual fees as a member of SNOMED *International* for 2025, 2026 and 2027.

Licenses

Distribute 3 new licenses of SNOMED CT clinical terminology to national partners.

Use Cases

Implement 2 new use cases.

Translated terms

Increase to 8562 the number of translated SNOMED CT terms.

Dissemination and Representation

Participate in official SNOMED *International* meetings and promote dissemination and communication activities.

Training

Organize 1 training action to support partners in using a new use case.

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News Link:

- [SPMS strengthens interoperability with SNOMED CT](#) (published on Feb. 20th, 2025)

Annex II. SNO-PT 2 webpage text in Portuguese

Portugal SNOMED International Membership 2

Âmbito

A ação SNO-PT 2, coordenada pela SPMS, visa assegurar a continuidade e expansão da utilização da terminologia internacional normalizada para a codificação de dados de saúde, a SNOMED CT, nos sistemas de informação de saúde nacionais. O uso desta terminologia é fundamental para incrementar a interoperabilidade semântica, suportando o desenvolvimento do Espaço Europeu de Dados de Saúde com vista à prestação de melhores cuidados de saúde a nível nacional e transfronteiriço (utilização primária) e também para fins de investigação, inovação médica, formulação de políticas de saúde e atividades de regulação (utilização secundária), contribuindo assim para a melhoria da qualidade dos dados de saúde disponíveis para esses objetivos.

Impacto para o Serviço Nacional de Saúde (SNS)

A utilização de um conjunto de terminologias normalizadas internacionalmente nos cuidados de saúde, como a SNOMED CT, promove a interoperabilidade, a qualidade dos cuidados de saúde e a eficiência na gestão da informação clínica. É uma ferramenta essencial para a modernização e digitalização do SNS, permitindo um acesso mais seguro, eficiente e estruturado à informação clínica. O seu impacto vai além da interoperabilidade, contribuindo para um sistema de saúde mais interligado, inovador e centrado no cidadão.

Melhoria da Interoperabilidade e Comunicação entre Sistemas

Facilitando a troca de informação entre diferentes sistemas de saúde, hospitais, clínicas e profissionais.

Suporte à Saúde Digital e Registos de Saúde Eletrónicos

A integração da SNOMED CT nos sistemas de RSE do SNS melhora a codificação e recuperação de dados clínicos.

Melhoria na Prestação de Cuidados de Saúde

Com um vocabulário padronizado, os profissionais de saúde têm acesso a informações mais precisas sobre os doentes.

Apoio à Investigação e Inovação Médica

Os dados estruturados e normalizados viabilizam análises epidemiológicas, estudos clínicos e o desenvolvimento de novas abordagens médicas.

Sustentabilidade e Eficiência na Gestão do SNS

A adoção da SNOMED CT contribui para uma gestão mais eficiente dos recursos de saúde.

Objetivos da ação SNO-PT 2

De 1 de janeiro de 2025 até dezembro de 2027:

Anuidade

Garantir 3 anuidades como membro da SNOMED *International* relativas a 2025, 2026 e 2027.

Licenças

Distribuir 3 novas licenças da terminologia clínica SNOMED CT a parceiros nacionais.

Casos de Uso

Implementar 2 novos casos de uso.

Termos traduzidos

Aumentar para 8562, o número de termos SNOMED CT traduzidos.

Divulgação e Representação

Participar em reuniões oficiais da SNOMED *International* e promover atividades de divulgação e comunicação.

Formação

Organizar 1 ação de formação para apoiar os parceiros na utilização de um novo caso de uso.

Notícias

SPMS reforça interoperabilidade com SNOMED CT

A SPMS continua a investir na melhoria da comunicação entre sistemas de tecnologias de informação e comunicação (TIC) no setor da saúde, incentivando o uso da terminologia clínica SNOMED CT em Portugal.

Ler mais – SPMS

Resultados alcançados

A publicar em janeiro de 2026.

A ação SNO-PT 2 é cofinanciado pela União Europeia, Programa EU4Health 2021-2027 ao abrigo do Grant Agreement (Acordo de Subvenção) Nº 101181370. No entanto, os pontos de vista e opiniões expressos são exclusivamente da responsabilidade do(s) autor(es) e não refletem necessariamente os da União Europeia ou da Agência Europeia de Execução para a Saúde e o Digital (European Health and Digital Executive Agency, HaDEA). Nem a União Europeia nem a autoridade concedente podem ser responsabilizados por eles.

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News Link:

- [SPMS reforça interoperabilidade com SNOMED CT \(2025-02-20\)](#)

For more information:

<https://www.ctc.min-saude.pt/sno-pt-2/>

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